

MORPHO-CULTURAL CHARACTERISTICS OF LACTIC ACID BACTERIA ISOLATED FROM SPONTANEOUS FERMENTED DAIRY PRODUCTS USED IN ZANGILAN REGION

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Abstract. *As a result of research, six different lactic acid bacteria strains were isolated from yoghurt samples taken from the villages of Mammadbayli and Agali in Zangilan district. The isolated strains differed in colony size, colour, surface structure, and edge shape. In terms of cell form, five of the six strains (BDU-MƏ-1, BDU-MƏ-2.1, BDU-MƏ-2.2, BDU-MƏ-2.3, BDU-AĞ-2.1) were cocci-shaped, while one (BDU-AĞ-2.2) was rod-shaped.*

Keywords: *fermented dairy product, lactic acid bacteria, strain, morpho-cultural characteristics.*

Lactic acid bacteria are microorganisms that play an important role in the food industry, especially in the production of fermented dairy products. In addition to contributing to the taste, texture, and storage properties of the product, they are also significant for human health due to their probiotic properties. Locally prepared fermented dairy products are of particular interest in terms of microbial diversity, and the study of regional bacterial strains is both practically and scientifically relevant.

Zangilan district is one of the regions rich in biodiversity due to its natural and ecological features. It is inevitable that homemade spontaneous yoghurt products in this area contain various strains of lactic acid bacteria. Therefore, isolating lactic acid bacteria strains from yoghurt samples taken from different villages of Zangilan district and studying their morpho-cultural properties is essential for identification.

The aim of this study was to isolate lactic acid bacteria strains from spontaneous yoghurt samples collected in Mammadbayli and Agali villages of Zangilan district and to comparatively study their morpho-cultural properties.

As research material, yoghurt samples were taken from two different areas of Mammadbayli village (Mammadbayli 1 and Mammadbayli 2) and from Agali village. The samples were collected under sterile conditions, transported to the microbiology laboratory within six hours, and experiments were carried out.

For the isolation of lactic acid bacteria from yoghurt samples, the dilution method was used. After inoculation, the colonies formed were evaluated according to morphological and cultural characteristics. Colony size, colour, shape, surface structure, edge character, and degree of mucosity were considered, and separate strains were distinguished and named accordingly.

In the yoghurt sample taken from Mammadbayli 1 village, only one type of microbial colony was observed. The isolated strain was named BDU-MƏ-1. Its colonies were small, pinpoint-shaped, white, with slightly raised surfaces. Colony diameter varied between 0.5–1 mm. The cell form was cocci-shaped.

In the yoghurt sample taken from Mammadbayli 2 village, three different colonies were observed. BDU-MƏ-2.1 small, pinpoint-shaped, white colonies with smooth edges and shiny surfaces. Diameter 0.5–1 mm cocci-shaped cells. BDU-MƏ-2.2 yellowish colonies, slightly raised, dry and wrinkled. Diameter 2–3 mm, edges slightly wavy, cocci-shaped cells. These features clearly distinguished the strain from others.

Colonies of the BDU-MƏ-2.3 strain were larger in size, reaching a diameter of 8–10 mm. The colonies were whitish in colour, with irregular margins and a shiny, mucous surface structure. The cells of this strain were cocci-shaped. The mucous colony morphology suggests that this strain may have the ability to synthesise exopolysaccharides.

In the yoghurt sample collected from Agali village, two types of colonies were identified. Colonies of the BDU–AĞ-2.1 strain were pinpoint-shaped, white in colour, with smooth edges and surfaces, and had a diameter of 0.5–1 mm; the cell form was cocci-shaped. The colony morphology of this strain was similar to that of the BDU–MƏ-1 and BDU–MƏ-2.1 strains.

BDU–AĞ-2.2 colonies with diameter 3–6 mm, colour changing from whitish cream in the centre to more transparent at the edges, smooth edges, semi-shiny surface. Unlike the other strains, the cell form was rod-shaped.

Thus, it was determined that yoghurt samples taken from different villages within the same district showed diversity in the morpho-cultural characteristics of lactic acid bacteria. As a result of the study, six different lactic acid bacteria strains were isolated from yoghurt samples collected in Mammadbayli and Agali villages of Zangilan district. The strains differed in colony size, colour, surface structure, and edge shape. In terms of cell form, five strains (BDU–MƏ-1, BDU–MƏ-2.1, BDU–MƏ-2.2, BDU–MƏ-2.3, AĞ-2.1) were cocci-shaped, while one (BDU–AĞ-2.2) was rod-shaped.

The results suggest that locally prepared fermented dairy products are rich in lactic acid bacteria and possess diverse microbiota. These strains may be considered promising for future studies in terms of probiotic properties, technological potential, and identification.

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